

Assessing Awareness and Evaluating the Impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) Among Small Business Owners

“A Case Study of Satna City, Madhya Pradesh”

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Abstract: *GST (Goods and Services Tax) is a visionary step. The implementation of the GST has reduced the tax burden and improved the ease of doing business in the country. The impact of GST is weighted into two main parts; one for businesses and one for customers who actually bear the cost of the tax. India's unorganized sector and parts of industry, those who benefit from the exemption will also contribute significantly to the country's GDP growth. The fundamental objective of carrying out this study was to understand the level of GST awareness among small entrepreneurs and to assess the real impact they face. It is well known that the impact will impact manufacturing or sales, but to understand the magnitude and satisfaction of the impact, a study is needed. The research is based on a survey in which data was collected from 50 business people living in Satna. The tool used to collect the data is a structured questionnaire. The results obtained after the analysis showed that traders understand the implementation of GST and consider it a fair taxation system, but it needs clearer and simplified procedures as they have to rely on CAs for online declarations. The document attempts to test the real impact of the GST and ends with suggested measures.*

Keywords: Goods and Services Tax (GST), Value Added Tax (VAT), Central Tax.

JEL Classification: H20, H25, H71

Introduction: The sole source of revenue for the Government of India is taxation, and the main source of taxation is indirect tax, also known as GST, which is defined as "one tax, one country". Prior to July 1, 2017, many state taxes levied in the name of indirect taxes such as luxury tax, value added tax, state tax, central tax, acquisition tax, head tax, amusement tax, lottery tax, state supplementary tax, etc., and central tax, such as central consumption tax, service tax, special surtax customs, etc. implement. Imagine the tax burden on the payer and the many calculations that must be made to pay each tax. This caused confusion among traders.

The introduction of the GST has eliminated the formation of indirect taxes by introducing online GST filing. Another major goal of the GST is to eliminate cascading effects, although many believe this has yet to be achieved. The cascading effect refers to "taxes on taxes" that co-ordinately raise the prices of products, thereby causing inflation in the economy. The meaning of GST includes the system of double taxation, ie. Central TPS (CGST), State TPS (SGST), Integrated TPS (IGST). If

the location of the supplier and the buyer are in the same state, the seller must collect CGST and SGST from the buyer, and the central and state governments will agree on the appropriate distribution. This reduces cascading effects and simplifies the tax structure. The government implies interest rates on a reciprocal basis, but not exceeding 14%. The rates introduced vary from 5%, 12%, 18%, 28%, but alcohol/beverages, electricity and petroleum products are excluded from the GST rate. One of the main reasons why oil is not included in the GST is that the government gets huge revenue from around 28% of the revenue and the introduction of the GST will end their revenue. The same reason is that in some states, more than 50% of revenue comes from the sale of alcohol, in addition to alcohol GST. Electricity is a necessity, so keep it cheap and affordable, and some parties may promise cheaper electricity, which citizens can dilute.

The implications of the GST are no easy task and getting 1.33 billion people to understand the new system, especially where people are reluctant to accept change, is the biggest challenge. Listing the goods and services at a specific rate and explaining this will solve most problems. During the first few days, the prices of many goods and services rose, creating inflation in the economy. The lack of clarity on the improvements introduced in the economy softened the spirit. Many companies still do not have a proper IT structure to create GST invoices and extract required reports, which also includes a lack of properly trained resources and retraining of managers, which places an additional burden on departments. It is difficult for startups to deal with GST because they are not well established in the industry and they need to understand the new tax regime. Finally, we can say that the GST brings transparency and a broader platform to taxation. Eliminating corruption from a system is not easy, but it can be reduced to some extent.

Review of Literature:

- **Kaur (2018)** the aim of the study is to understand people's perception of GST and people's expectations after GST implementation. The study concluded that people are still not very aware of GST and they view the act negatively due to lack of proper information. It also displays information about goods and services that are missing answers and fails to identify forms that have already been completed.
- **Mishra (2018)** this study provides an overview of these ratios. It examines the impact of the GST on pharmaceuticals, agriculture, textiles, mobile phones and accessories, the telecommunications sector, real government, consumer goods, automobiles, banking and finance. The research report concludes that the impact of the flat tax scheme will attract more manufacturers to participate in the industry. Individuals will also benefit because the price of the product will be fixed and consumption will increase, which will lead to an increase in GDP. An increase in GDP will attract foreign investment, which will directly or indirectly create job opportunities.

- **Chouhan et.al. (2017)** the study looked at the brand awareness of 148 small business owners in Rajasthan. He also welcomes the difficulties faced by small business owners due to the lack of adequate knowledge and legal remedies. The main issue was customers refusing to pay GST, which created problems when filing taxes, and other issues that respondents perceived as tax difficulties due to the inclusion of technology in the process. Respondent's awareness was low to medium, primarily due to their reluctance to support the bill.
- **Banik and Das (2017)** this study reveals the challenges Indian economy is facing after the impact of GST, it reveals the comparison of GST with preview tax system, there are 31 types of taxes including the sales tax, state tax, etc. Now it becomes CGST, IGST, SGST, which makes the tax structure more complicated. Integrating technology into GST filling requires an increase in trained personnel. The change in GST rates has added to the confusion for small vendors and traders. The study concludes that further simplification of the law is needed as GDP will fall due to the introduction of an unplanned tax regime.

Research GAP: It is clear from the literature that VAT is an emerging issue in economic research. At the macro level, a lot of research has been done, but at the micro level and in semi-urban areas, nothing has been done. With this in mind, the study aimed to determine the level of awareness and impact of GST among small business owners in Madhya Pradesh, Satna city.

Objective of the study:

1. To assess the impact of GST on business owners residing in the city of Satna.
2. To Determine knowledge of GST among business owners residing in Satna city.

Research Methodology: The study was descriptive in nature, its SME owners were selected from respondents who were engaged in various businesses in the city of Satna. This chapter is divided into three parts:

- **Sources of Data:** Primary data is mainly collected directly through questionnaires. The study uses secondary data to support and corroborate the original data and form a solid theoretical basis. Secondary data is collected from research papers, SSRN, shodhganga, local institutes, research journals, journals, articles, GST portals, working papers, etc.
- **Sample Size:** 50 Small business owners.
- **Sampling Technique:** Convenience techniques are applied in non-probability sampling methods.

**Part “A”
DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERIZES**

Particulars	Frequency in Percentage
Gender	
Male	100%
Female	0%
Age	
18 – 30	12%
30 – 50	54%
50 above	32%
Literacy Level	
Illiterate	0%
Up to Sr. Secondary	36%
Graduation	52%
Post-Graduation	12%
Occupation	
Farmer	0%
Businessman	96%
Job	4%
Daily Wages	0%
Others	0%
Monthly Family Income	
Less than Rs 5000/-	4%
Rs 5000 – 15000	14%
Rs 15000 – 30000	34%
Rs 30000 and above	48%
Religion	
Hindu	42%
Muslim	12%
Christian	6%
Sikh	16%
Jain	20%
Any other	4%
Type of Area	
Urban	96%
Semi urban	0%
Rural	4%
Remote area	0%
Nature of Family	
Joint family	36%
Nuclear family	64%

Source: Computed (Figures in Percentage)

Demographic Characteristics: A survey was conducted with 50 people to find out the demographic characteristics of the respondents. It was found that of the 50 people who responded, 100% of the respondents were male. About 12% of the respondents were between 18 and 30 years old, 54% between 30 and 50 years old and 34% were 50 years old or older. About 34% of the respondents had secondary education, 52% of the respondents were university graduates and 12% of the respondents were graduate students, which show that the level of education in the Satna region is good. 96% of respondents were businessmen, while 4% had a job. 4% of respondents have a monthly family income

of less than 5,000, about 14% of respondents have a monthly income of 5,000 to 15,000, and 34% of respondents have a monthly income of 15,000 to 30,000. 48% of people have a monthly income above 30,000, which shows that the income level of the respondents is relatively high.

Part “B”

Particulars	Frequency in Percentage
How many responded has GST awareness	
Yes	100%
No	0%
What was the source of awareness?	
Friends/ family	22%
Media	52%
Internet	26%
Teacher	-
Others	-
Does GST is burden for people?	
Yes	18%
No	82%
Is GST is a fair tax system?	
Yes	48%
No	16%
Is available legislation is satisfactory in relation to GST?	
Yes – satisfactory	30%
No – need more clarity	70%
GST is easier than early tax system.	
Yes	88%
No	12%
What kind of tax GST is?	
Indirect Tax	100%
Direct Tax	-
Who is the Head of GST council of India?	
Mr. Narendra Modi	4%
Dr. Rajeev Kumar	6%
Mr. Arun Jaitely	26%
None	64%
Does the business is registered under GST?	
Yes	92%
No	8%
Do the have Knowledge about GST online portal?	
Yes	100%
No	-
Does the available legislation in relation to propose GST is satisfying?	
Yes – satisfactory	18%
No – Need more clarity	82%
Does the respondents current software equipped is capable enough to handle the proposed GST?	
Yes	92%
No	8%
Need assistance of lawyer or CA while filling the tax?	
Required	60%
Not required	40%

The table shows that respondents are well aware of the existence of the GST and its incorporation into bills passed by Parliament, suggesting that respondents are very aware of the changes in the way the tax is implemented. work. The table below shows that the most important source of knowledge is the media, followed by the Internet, which clearly limits people's greater exposure to the media and the Internet, which are the fastest and fastest sources of information. Easiest for the public. The media had the greatest influence on respondents. A third record shows that the majority of respondents do not see the GST as a burden on income, and this alleviates the main drawback of the old tax filing system. While some respondents felt that more should be added to the current law to reduce other impacted factors. Respondents were relieved by the changes to the tax reporting system. Record 4 shows that most of the respondents said that the implementation of the consumption tax is a fair tax and is accepted by the respondents, which shows that the respondents accepted and welcomed the system change, but some respondents are not satisfied with the implementation Excise tax , further reforms of the current tax system are needed. Record 4 shows the majority of respondents, viz. 70% would like more explanation of current VAT legislation, indicating that VAT legislation is a complex concept requiring more explanation and abstraction, which was more relaxed among respondents. While 30% of respondents were satisfied with the legislation, no further clarification was requested.

A record number of six indicated that 88% of respondents believed the GST meant much better than the previous tax system, with filling and maintaining tax entries easier, more reliable and more flexible. This reduces additional workload and paperwork. Only 12% of respondents felt that VAT is complicated and not easy to accept without a lot of help. Record 7 shows that 100% of respondents clearly stated that VAT is an indirect tax, which indicates that each respondent knows very well what type of tax it is. There are two types of taxation in the country, direct tax and indirect tax, and the meaning of GST is where the indirect tax is filed by the organization.

Records showed that 92 percent of the respondents were registered for GST, indicating that Satna City has a majority of taxpayers and the business is being conducted within limits set by the government. Only 4% of respondents are not VAT registered due to new market entry or business change/expansion. Business registration is carried out in accordance with the rules and regulations prescribed by the government. The results show that 100% of respondents know about GST online portals via media, internet, friends also know about new ways to integrate, include to file GST and get refund from government. The GST online portal reduces paperwork and makes filing taxes easier. The government announces the latest date through sources, remembers the date, files taxes and refunds. In short, they were completely satisfied with the introduction of the new changes to the legislation, while 82% responded to the introduction of the legislation by asking for further clarification and asking for help with ore losses in the pits and ebbs.

Part "C"

Particular	Frequency in Percentage
<i>Reduction of corruption in the economy</i>	
Highly Agreed	12%
Agreed	62%
Neutral	18%
Less agreed	8%
Fully Disagreed	-
Total	100%
<i>GST legislation is satisfactory</i>	
Highly Agreed	-
Agreed	42%
Neutral	28%
Less agreed	26%
Fully Disagreed	4%
Total	100%
<i>Ease in filing of GST online</i>	
Highly Agreed	38%
Agreed	38%
Neutral	16%
Less agreed	8%
Fully Disagreed	-
Total	100%
<i>Rate implication on the occupation satisfactory</i>	
Highly Agreed	18%
Agreed	18%
Neutral	14%
Less agreed	46%
Fully Disagreed	4%
Total	100%
Benefit of the government schemes.	
Highly Agreed	-
Agreed	18%
Neutral	36%
Less agreed	46%
Fully Disagreed	-
Total	100%
Applied existence law is fairly applied.	
Highly Agreed	10%
Agreed	32%
Neutral	10%
Less agreed	44%
Fully Disagreed	4%
Total	100%
Present system is beneficial then early tax system.	
Highly Agreed	30%
Agreed	34%
Neutral	16%
Less agreed	12%
Fully Disagreed	8%
Total	100%
Necessary amendments should be introduces timely in the legislation	
Highly Agreed	60%

Agreed	32%
Neutral	8%
Less agreed	-
Fully Disagreed	-
Total	100%
Government is taking corrective measures for the flexibility in the current taxation system.	
Highly Agreed	8%
Agreed	32%
Neutral	40%
Less agreed	16%
Fully Disagreed	4%
Total	100%
Inflation cost reduced due to GST.	
Highly Agreed	6%
Agreed	32%
Neutral	12%
Less agreed	38%
Fully Disagreed	12%
Total	100%
Present tax system moved the pace of economy growth.	
Highly Agreed	30%
Agreed	52%
Neutral	10%
Less agreed	6%
Fully Disagreed	2%
Total	100%
GST affected the income.	
Highly Agreed	48%
Agreed	12%
Neutral	24%
Less agreed	8%
Fully Disagreed	-
Total	100%
Implementation of GST increased the documentary procedure.	
Highly Agreed	10%
Agreed	50%
Neutral	4%
Less agreed	34%
Fully Disagreed	2%
Total	100%
Implementation of GST reduced the manual work.	
Highly Agreed	44%
Agreed	16%
Neutral	8%
Less agreed	24%
Fully Disagreed	8%
Total	100%
GST made it mandatory to provide the bill to customer.	
Highly Agreed	32%
Agreed	28%
Neutral	36%
Less agreed	4%
Fully Disagreed	-

Total	100%
E – WAY bill is beneficial for business.	
Highly Agreed	32%
Agreed	28%
Neutral	28%
Less agreed	8%
Fully Disagreed	4%
Total	100%

Findings:

1. GST procedures require consulting a CA because 60% of respondents have no training.
2. "The GST reduces corruption" supported the statement with 62% of the vote. Eno
3. 82% respondents are in favour of GST that it's not a burden.
4. 42% of respondents were less than satisfied with the interest rate implications. Only 18% of respondents were satisfied with the default rate.
5. 82%, responded required more clarity in the legislation.
6. The GST has failed to reduce inflation in the economy, with a majority of around 50% believing that the GST has failed to reduce inflation.
7. A majority of around 80% of the responded are in the favour of the statement that GDP has increased the pace of economy growth.
8. The introduction of GST has increased the documentation process while reducing manual labor by providing online registration during the tax filing process. More than 50% of respondents answered that the GST increased their documentation as they had to proofread each transaction, while the introduction of online tax filing reduced their manual work as they had to submit estimate forms with the required information.
9. In the survey, it was found that 60% of respondents felt that e-invoicing would be beneficial for businesses, it reduces the documentation process as provincial documentation has been eliminated, the system is user-friendly and easy to generate bills.

Suggestions:

1. The GST Board should strive to simplify the GST process.
2. The rates implemented should be modulated.
3. GST training sessions should be organized regularly, especially in semi-urban areas.

Conclusion:

In the era of globalization, an internationally competitive India requires a sound and systematic tax structure. GST will not only bring transparency, but also facilitate ease of use. Previously, each state had its own tax rates, which were complex and raised commodity prices through a trickle-down effect, which also discouraged foreign direct investment. In this study, respondents were very aware of the GST law and tax rates imposed on products, but small

entrepreneurs were not very satisfied with the tax rates. The new rules for filing taxes online were appreciated by respondents for the significant time savings and reduction in paperwork. 62% of respondents agree that corruption has decreased due to the introduction of the GST in the economy. The majority of respondents believed that the GST would certainly increase the country's economic growth rate, but more clarity was needed, as the study suggests. The GST Council should continue its efforts to stimulate the Indian economy.

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